

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN'S COOPERATION WITH THE SHANGHAI COOPERATION ORGANIZATION IN THE FIELDS OF SECURITY AND ECONOMY

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Abstract. *This article examines the importance of Uzbekistan's cooperation with the Shanghai Cooperation Organization in economic and security fields. It discusses Uzbekistan's membership in the SCO, the growth of trade relations, and the expansion of export and import cooperation with member states. The paper also highlights the role of the SCO in strengthening regional transport, energy, infrastructure, and investment projects. In addition, it analyzes cooperation in combating terrorism, extremism, drug trafficking, and cyber threats. The study concludes that SCO partnership supports Uzbekistan's economic development, regional integration, strategic security, improvement of the population's socio-economic well-being, and long-term diplomatic interests in Eurasia today.*

Keywords: *economic cooperation, Shanghai Cooperation Organization, Uzbekistan, security cooperation, foreign trade, regional integration, transport logistics.*

Introduction

The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) is a regional international structure that was established in 1996–1997 under the name “Shanghai Five” and was officially named the “Shanghai Cooperation Organization” in 2001 after Uzbekistan joined as a full member. At present, the SCO includes China, Russia, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and, after 2017, India and Pakistan; Iran joined in 2023, and Belarus joined in 2024. It also has two observer states, Afghanistan and Mongolia, and many dialogue partners, such as Azerbaijan, Turkey, Saudi Arabia, and others. In most cases, SCO members rely on the principles of the multifaceted “Shanghai Spirit,” which is based on mutual trust, respect for interests, and support for the path of peace [1].

Uzbekistan's chairmanship of the SCO in 2021–2022 demonstrated a high level of activity within this structure. It is known that during this period, more than 80 events were held within the framework of the SCO under the leadership of the President of Uzbekistan [3]. At subsequent summits, issues related to international peace, trade-economic and investment cooperation, transport and communication corridors, food security, and joint efforts in the field of climate were put forward.

At the same time, as the global geopolitical situation becomes increasingly complex, the SCO is gaining importance for many member states as an alternative and inclusive platform for integration against protectionism [2]. The continuous increase in the number of member states of this international organization certainly serves as an important factor in improving the economic

potential of developing countries that are members of the organization. The expansion of areas of cooperation brings the state economy and the population's standard of living to a new stage [5; 6].

Our state is consistently increasing its activity in this regard. In particular, the growing number of areas of cooperation among SCO member states and the annual increase in export and import volumes clearly demonstrate Uzbekistan's position in the Central Asian region.

Figure 1. The map of the SCO member states shows cooperating countries in red. This map clearly shows the SCO members and Uzbekistan's position in the region.

Economic Cooperation

Economic cooperation within the SCO is an especially important direction for Uzbekistan, as member states occupy a significant place as trade and economic partners. In particular, Uzbekistan's total trade turnover with SCO countries increased 2.5 times in 2017–2024, rising from USD 12.9 billion to USD 32.5 billion [1; 2].

During this period, Uzbekistan's exports to SCO countries increased from USD 5.8 billion to USD 9.0 billion, while imports rose from USD 7.1 billion to USD 23.5 billion. As a result, in 2024, SCO countries accounted for approximately 33.4% of Uzbekistan's exports, amounting to USD 9.0 billion. However, due to the high share of gold in exports, when gold is excluded, the share of exports to SCO countries was around 46.3% [1; 2].

Naturally, the share of trade with SCO countries in total foreign trade is significant. In 2024, this figure was around 49.4%, while in 2017 it was 48.6%. According to changes in this gradually increasing share, Uzbekistan is partly diversifying its exports of valuable commodities such as oil and gold to SCO countries, while imports are mainly focused on industrial products [4].

For example, in 2024, trade turnover among the main trading partners within the SCO was distributed as follows: China — USD 12.50 billion, or 38.4%; Russia — USD 11.63 billion, or 35.7%; Kazakhstan — USD 4.28 billion, or 13.1%. In terms of exports, Russia was the leader with USD 3.70 billion, or 40.9%, followed by China with USD 2.10 billion, or 22.8%, and Kazakhstan with USD 1.45 billion, or 16.1%. In terms of imports, China played the leading role with USD 10.43 billion, or 44.3%, followed by Russia with USD 7.95 billion, or 33.8%, and Kazakhstan with USD 2.83 billion, or 12% [1; 2; 3].

When viewed graphically, over the past few years SCO countries have maintained a large share of about 50% in Uzbekistan's commodity imports, while the share in exports, excluding

gold, amounted to 46%. In general, after our country became a member of the SCO, we can see that cooperation in every field has been growing positively. This is one of the important factors in improving the living standards of the population [4].

The table below presents Uzbekistan–SCO trade indicators for 2017, 2023, and 2024, especially showing that the sharp increase in import volume was caused by the growth of imports of Russian and Chinese products, which increased total trade turnover.

Figure 2. Economic cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the Shanghai international organization.

Cooperation has also become more active in other areas of economic cooperation, particularly in energy, infrastructure, and transport. Great attention is being paid to road transport, railway, and transit-logistics projects among SCO members. Uzbekistan is strengthening relations with China, Kazakhstan, and other SCO states in joint energy projects and in the supply of gas and oil. In particular, during the 2023–2024 SCO summits, issues related to expanding partnership in energy and transport were discussed [6].

For example, at the 2025 summit in Tianjin, the declaration set goals for “strengthening cooperation in the fields of energy and transport.” SCO members have been assisting one another in the construction of gas and oil facilities, electricity transmission, and ensuring the import of agricultural products [6].

Regional transport projects are especially relevant for Uzbekistan. For example, the construction of the “China–Kyrgyzstan–Uzbekistan” railway, proposed by the leaders of the countries, is expected to significantly shorten freight routes along the corridor between Central Asia and Western Asia and increase transit potential. As noted by Kun.uz and other sources, infrastructure projects in this direction will further strengthen regional integration within the framework of the “One Belt, One Road” initiative [2].

The 2025 SCO summit signage in Tianjin, China, also shows that transport-logistics cooperation projects within the SCO are creating opportunities for Uzbekistan to become a major transport hub in Eurasia. In the areas of investment and financing, Uzbekistan is putting forward proposals to create joint mechanisms with SCO members, for example, the SCO Development Bank [5].

Cooperation in the Field of Security

One of the main priority areas of the SCO is ensuring regional security. In particular, the prevention of terrorism, extremism, and drug trafficking is a matter regularly discussed in the SCO's Dushanbe Declaration and other documents. Every year, cooperation programs on combating terrorism, separatism, and extremism are reviewed within the framework of the organization [4; 5].

Uzbekistan pays great attention to regional anti-terrorist structures within the SCO. For example, in addition to the Regional Anti-Terrorist Structure located in Tashkent, the SCO Public Diplomacy Center, the meeting mechanism of the heads of railway administrations, and the Silk Road Tourism Institute have been opened in Tashkent. This further strengthens Uzbekistan's importance in regional security [1].

The threat of terrorism and extremism is especially recognized as coming from the territory of Afghanistan. The situation in Afghanistan has been discussed many times at SCO summits. At the 2023 summit, the issue of establishing peace was noted as a strategic task for all members. Uzbekistan also pays great attention to its contribution to assisting Afghanistan and ensuring regional stability through the SCO platform.

Within the framework of military cooperation, SCO member states regularly conduct command-staff military exercises such as "Peace Mission." For example, in September 2021, military personnel from Russia, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, China, Pakistan, India, and Uzbekistan participated in the "Peace Mission-2021" exercise held in Russia. Such joint exercises serve to exchange experience among SCO members in areas such as coordinating operational indicators, cybersecurity, and preventing radicalization among young people [6].

During the "Peace Mission-2021" exercise, Uzbek military personnel demonstrated their military skills in various areas, including movement in military vehicles, effective use of firearms, and infantry movement on land and water. Within the framework of SCO command-staff exercises, Uzbek military personnel successfully completed training exercises with Russian military personnel on the effective use of firearms [6].

Cooperation in the field of cybersecurity has also been established within the SCO. For example, Uzbek and Chinese officials recently discussed the development of mutual cooperation in cybersecurity. In addition, within the framework of meetings of the secretaries of the SCO Security Councils, joint measures are being taken to coordinate the activities of law enforcement agencies and combat cyber threats.

SCO members have also established the exchange of experience in such areas as preventing radicalization among young people, exchanging information, and training security specialists. In its practical scope, the SCO serves as a platform for "multifaceted cooperation" aimed at maintaining peace and stability. As emphasized in the organization's public information, Uzbekistan conducts its activities within the SCO based on the principles of pragmatism and initiative, and the development of partnership with the SCO remains one of the priority directions of Uzbekistan's foreign policy [6].

Conclusion

For our country, strong cooperation with the Shanghai Cooperation Organization is not only a source of economic benefit but also a means of ensuring regional security and strategic interests. The expansion of trade relations with SCO members helps open new markets for Uzbekistan's exports and ensures the import of necessary products.

At the same time, cooperation between the armed forces and law enforcement agencies of partner states makes the fight against extremism and terrorism more effective. The SCO's potential

for regional integration and multilateral cooperation serves the sustainable development of Uzbekistan. Coordination of transport and logistics strategies, attraction of new projects and investments, as well as joint activities on the transition to a “green” and digital economy are being carried out on a regular basis.

In general, multifaceted cooperation with the SCO is a strategic priority for Uzbekistan. As an equal member of the organization, Uzbekistan is interested in further strengthening its position and expanding partnership in all areas. Strengthening relations with the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization based on the principles of friendship and solidarity is an important contribution of Uzbekistan to regional peace and sustainable development.

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